

Manufacturing & Characterization of Glass Samples with Three Different Sources of Silica: Possible Alternatives for Quartz in Glass Manufacturing.

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Abstract

Pure silica sources as quartz, quartzite, and glassmaker's sand are traditionally used for commercial glass manufacturing. Limitation of sources, degradation of purity with the change in mining and processing techniques, very high fusion temperature, and import dependence make them costly and non-feasible in most cases. The research is to investigate the possibility of using locally available silica sources and silica-rich wastage material which can reduce the cost and enhance environmental safety. Quartz, calcined Rice Husk Ash (RHA), and Padma River sand were used as silica sources to manufacture three types of glass samples respectively, with similar composition. The glasses were characterized for physical properties, chemical stability, thermal shock resistance, softening point, microhardness, and optical properties. The results of these tests revealed that the use of both RHA and Padma River sand, especially of river sand, as an alternative for quartz reduced the porosity, acidic corrosion, transition range temperature and also increased the thermal shock resistance and fracture toughness of the glass samples with a little fluctuation in colors. These indicate it is highly realistic and cost-efficient to use locally available river sand or RHA in glass products that do not require a high degree of optical specifications.

Key Words: Glass Manufacturing, RHA, Padma River Sand, Microhardness, Optical Properties.

1. Introduction

Glass is one of the most manufactured materials used for multipurpose applications ranges from construction, commodities to hi-tech electronics and appliances. Conventionally glass is defined as a supercooled liquid which is an amorphous solid completely lacking in long-range, periodic atomic structure, and exhibiting a region of glass transformation behavior (**Shelby, 2005**). Simply, any material, which exhibits glass transformation behavior is a glass. The bulk of the glasses manufactured around the world is silicate glasses or in particularly soda-lime-silicate glasses formed by melting. The main constituents of soda-lime-silicate glasses are silica as glass former, soda as a fluxing agent which lowers the melting temperature of silica (>2000° C) within a practical limit (<1600° C) (**Doremus, 1994**), and lime as a property modifier which encounters the degradation occurs due to fluxing action. As pure silica products such as vitreous silica (100% pure fused silica) require a high degree of purity of raw materials, high fusion temperature, it is often considered highly uneconomical to use pure silica raw material i.e. quartz in construction or commodity-based glass products. Therefore, glass industries had

turned into glass maker's sand as an alternative of quartz long ago. This is silica-rich sand found at different shores of north-western Africa, America, and Mediterranean coasts (Burciard, 1905). But due to the high level of unplanned and mammoth scale collection of these sands over the century, it has become a great threat to the environment and biodiversity of coastal regions. Therefore, alternatives for a sustainably usable source of raw material is highly suggested by scientists and environment workers.

Rice is one of the major harvested crops in the world as well as in Bangladesh. Especially in the 'Varendra' region, rice mills are one of the common scenarios observed at Naogaon-Santahar-Bogra rice belt. Rice mills around the world yield almost 20% of their total consumption as rice husk waste (An et al., 2010). Rice husks (RH) are mainly used as firewood activators and later the rice husk ashes (RHAs) are used as fertilizer or buried in to ground for disposal. But the high concentration of silica (>90 wt. %) (Pode, 2016) inhibits quick degradation of the ashes into the soil.

Another important source for silica is the river bed sands which cause a serious lacking of navigability and overflow of rivers during the rainy season. The mighty river 'Padma' in the north-western region of Bangladesh is now dying with this sand blockage. Frequent dredging is carried out and the sands are used for landfills or construction purposes. It has been reported that more than 85% of silica and some alkali minerals are present at Padma River Sand (PRS) (Rafi et al., 2018). These higher silica content along with these minerals can lead to denser and low-temperature process-able glass manufacturing.

Therefore, this study aims at turning these two; one, long time degradation required agro-waste and another, hindering the flow of a cardiac of this riverine country to a possible alternative for quartz and glass maker's sand in glass manufacturing.

2. Materials & Methodology

Three types of silica sources i.e. quartz, RHA, PRS were used for manufacturing three different types of samples, S1, S2 & S3 respectively by the conventional melting process. A similar amount of flux (Na₂O) and lime were maintained for all three compositions stated in table.1.

Table.1: Composition of different samples.

Components	S1 (Wt. %)	S2 (Wt. %)	S3 (Wt. %)
Quartz	70	-	-
RHA	-	70	-
PRS	-	-	70
Na ₂ O	20	20	20
CaO	10	10	10

Sodium hydroxide was used as a starting batch material for sodium oxide and calcium carbonate for calcium oxide. The batch was prepared according to the gravimetric factor calculation and the raw materials were weighed, mixed, and placed in a muffle furnace at three separate ceramic crucibles. They were heated to a temperature of 1350° C and held for 30 minutes. The samples were then quenched at the steel plate and processed for testing. Density (apparent and true), and porosity was measured according to Archimedes' principle. The true density of the samples was calculated by grinding the samples and porosity was measured by a relative comparison of apparent and true densities. The chemical stability test was performed

by following ASTM C225-85 standards for chemical stability of glasses in acidic (Hydrogen fluoride Solution), basic (sodium hydroxide solution), and neutral (deionized water) media. The softening point of the samples was determined by the Labino method at Orton Softening Point Tester or Penetrometer, SP-3A (heating rate 25 °C/min.) Micro-hardness of the samples was measured by Struers Duramin-1/2 Micro-hardness Tester. Optical microscopy for surface irregularities and UV-Vis spectroscopy (SIMADZU UV-Vis -1650, Japan) was done for determining optical properties.

3. Results & Discussion

3.1. Density & Porosity:

The density and porosity of the samples are depicted in Fig.1. The apparent density of S1 was relatively lower than its true density and that yields a high degree of porosity. This porosity is due to the higher fusion temperature required for quartz (Shelby, 2005), the temperature of melting i.e. 1350 °C is not enough for the complete dissolution of quartz though some amount of fluxes are added. Further addition of fluxes and/or temperature may enhance the fusion of quartzite silica. But at the same temperature S2 and S3 fused very well and yields lower porosity. The change in densities is not as irregular in the case of S2 as RHA has some organic matter (Omatola et al., 2009) which reduces the melting temperature and a good viscosity of melt can be achieved. However, S3 has a lower porosity than the other two samples and a moderate density too. It's because the impurities present at PRS contain a reasonable amount of fluxing agents. These fluxing agents include Na₂O, K₂O, and refiner salts like NaCl, KCl, MgCl₂, etc. (Rafi et al., 2018). The higher the amount of fluxing element, the higher the density and lower the melting temperature and thus porosity (Hou et al., 2017). S3 shows better properties compared with other samples.

Fig.1: Densities & porosity of different glass samples.

3.2. Micro-Hardness:

Hardness refers to the resistance to penetration or plastic deformation. It is directly related to the internal components of the material, porosity, and surface finish of samples. For S3, due to

the presence of metallic oxides like Al_2O_3 , MgO , CaO , and other aluminosilicates from the impurities, the hardness value is higher (Kilinc & Hand, 2015). (Fig.2).

Fig.2: Vickers micro-hardness of different glass samples.

In general, the hardness value for quartz glass is higher than other glasses. But in this study, the results show a slight reduction of the hardness value than Padma sand sample i.e. S3 due to the presence of porosity (Jang & Matsubara, 2005) in the sample. Moreover, the HVN value is measured as an average of at least three indentations usually (four indentations have been taken for this sample), some of the indentations may have fallen on the porous surface and yielded smaller value. On the other hand, lower hardness in the case of S2 is due to the lower percentage of silica content than S1 and the presence of organic fiber-like materials which increases plastic deformation. (Webo et al., 2018) The Padma sand sample i.e. S3 has a higher fusion of silica, better density, and lower porosity as found in the test results described earlier. These have contributed to the higher hardness of the sample.

3.3. Softening Point:

The softening point is the first point at which glass starts to slump under its own weight. It is defined in terms of temperature at which the viscosity of $10^{7.65}$ is reached. The softening point indicates the thermal stability of any glass sample. It also provides an assumption about the range of glass transformation as it is the first point of change in glass from solid substance to liquid (Shelby, 2005). The softening point of different samples is shown in Fig.3. The PRS sample has the highest softening point because of the high density of the sample. Moreover, the metallic ions present in the sand (Rafi et al., 2018) as impurities, provide stable oxides phase at high temperatures. (Leśniak et al., 2019) The quartz sample has a similar higher softening point due to the higher percentages of silica which provides a high melting temperature. Meanwhile, rice husk ash usually doesn't contain many metallic oxides and silica content at that source has a high degree of organic and organo-chemical substances (An et al., 2010) which reduces the strength and hardness of the sample and makes it vulnerable to lower thermal load than the others.

Fig.3: Softening point of different glass samples.

Fig. 4: Corrosion rate of different glass Sample.

3.4 Chemical Stability

Chemical stability of glass samples is measured in terms of the corrosion rate of samples at different acidic and basic media. The corrosion rate for the three samples is shown in Fig.4. Glasses are usually resistant to chemical attacks because of the compact silica tetrahedron structure which requires very high stress to breach. Among the acidic media, soda-lime glasses are highly vulnerable to the attack of HF, some glasses readily dissolve at HF solution at high temperature. This is because of the direct attack on the Si-O bond of silica. (Varshneya & Seward III, 2001). So, high silica-containing sources [Quartz 99.5%, RHA (>95%), PRS (>80%)] undergo high HF corrosion [(Varshneya & Seward III, 2001), (Rafi et al., 2018), (Omatola et al., 2009)]. Consequently, S1 has the highest HF corrosion. This corrosion value

is much more augmented by the porosity of the sample. The alkali resistance of glasses is degraded by the presence of alkali ions which causes leaching out at hydroxide ions due to the ion exchange phenomenon (Kaur et al., 2013). Therefore, the PRS sample has the highest basic corrosion, and quartz has the lowest and the quartz sample doesn't possess any detectable basic corrosion.

3.5 Optical Properties

3.5.1 Visual & Microscopic Inspection:

The visual inspection of the samples indicates that the S1 has a higher transparent appearance but the presence of pores due to undissolved quartz and lack of bubbles removal are also visible. The S2 sample has a greenish look provided by the iron content of sand and the S3 sample with a whitish look from mesoporous silica content is also observed. The images of the sample along with the optical micrograph are presented in Fig.5 & Fig.6.

Fig.5: Image of the (a) S1, (b) S2 & (c) S3 glass samples in visual inspection.

Fig.6: Optical Micrograph of (a) S1, (b) S2 & (c) S3 Glass Sample.

3.5.2 UV-Vis Spectroscopy:

The transparency and absorbance graph from UV-Vis spectroscopy of S2 and S3 is shown in Fig.6 to get further information about the optical properties of these samples. It indicates that S3 has less absorbance thus contain better transparency than S2 but lower than the traditional fused silica or quartz glass i.e. S1. It is because, Padma sand contains a handsome amount of

alkaline earths (Rafi et al., 2018), which lower the dispersion and refractive index (Zallen, 1983). It also has a higher amount of alumina which replaces polarizable NBO's by less polarizable Al-O-Si bridging oxygen (Shelby, 2005) thus lowers the absorbance (< 0.4%) Fig.7 (a) and increases the transmittance Fig. 7(c). And vice versa occurs in the case of S3 Fig.7 (b) & (d) which is not provided by any alkaline earth or aluminosilicates.

Fig.7: Optical properties of glass samples: (a) absorbance of S2, (b) absorbance of S3, (c) transmittance of S2 & (d) transmittance of S3.

4. Conclusion

In this work, different sources of silica are used to manufacture soda-lime silicate glasses, and physical, mechanical, thermal, chemical, and optical properties are investigated. The results of these investigations show that at the fixed lower melting temperature, the S3 sample in which silica is provided by Padma River Sand, has relatively better properties in terms of density, porosity, hardness, softening point than other samples and moderate properties in chemical and optical characterizations. Therefore, it can be used as a cheap and efficient alternative for quartz glass or fused silica glass in applications that don't require very high optical and chemical specifications such as household utensils, artistic glassware, window-door or other structural glass components, etc. On the other hand, the S2 sample, silica source of which is Rice Husk Ash, shows lower softening point, high hardness, and optical absorbance which can be made efficient in low-temperature processing of glass and glass-ceramics used for biomedical, security, and ballistic applications.

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